

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Lab-scale and on-field industrial composting of biodegradable plastic blends for packaging [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

Zhi Kai Chong ¹, Marie Haye², Sharon Wilson¹, Ihsanullah Sohoo¹, Kerstin Kuchta¹

¹Circular Resource Engineering and Management (CREM), Hamburg University of Technology, Hamburg, 21073, Germany

²Department of Energy and Environmental Engineering (GEn), Institut National des Sciences Appliquées de Lyon, Villeurbanne, 69100, France

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Abstract

Background: The acceptance of compostable plastic packaging in industrial composting plants is not universal despite available certification for compostability due to the persistence of compostable plastic residues reported by some industrial plants. This study aims to better understand this discrepancy by comparing the disintegration rate of two compostable plastic blends designed for rigid packaging (polylactic acid based) and soft packaging (polybutylene succinate based) between a controlled lab-scale test and an on-field test in an industrial composting plant.

Methods: The thermophilic lab-scale disintegration test was conducted according to ISO 20200 in triplicates for 4, 8 and 12 weeks while the on-field test was conducted by exposing duplicate test material in the compost pile of an industrial composting plant in northern Germany, for three weeks. The mass change of the remaining test material >2mm was used as an indicator of disintegration.

Results: The rigid packaging blend (1 mm thickness) retained on average 76.4%, 59.0% and 55.7% of its mass after 4, 8 and 12 weeks respectively in the lab-scale test. After exposure to industrial composting on-field, the remaining mass was 97.2% and 99.5%. The soft packaging blend (109±9 µm sample thickness) retained on average 45.4%, 10.9% and 0.3% of its mass after 4, 8 and 12 weeks respectively and 94.0% and 93.8% after exposure to industrial composting on-field.

Conclusions: The results show a substantial difference in disintegration rates between the lab-scale and the on-field test after three to four weeks. The difference between the tests that might

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1. **Mehlika Karamanlioglu** , Istanbul Gelisim University, İstanbul, Turkey

2. **Douglas G. Hayes** , University of Tennessee, Knoxville, USA

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contribute significantly to the differing disintegration rates is the composition of the composting substrate. Besides the design and characteristics of the packaging itself, the composting substrate and thermophilic composting duration of individual plants are important to determine the suitability of treating compostable plastic packaging in industrial composting plants as well as inform potential solutions.

Keywords

Biodegradable plastic, compostable plastic, compostable packaging, industrial composting, polylactic acid, polybutylene succinate

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Corresponding author: Zhi Kai Chong (kai.chong@tuhh.de)

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Plain language summary

There is resistance from industrial composting plants to the treatment of compostable biodegradable plastics. This study aims to compare the disintegration rates of two new biodegradable plastic blends developed for rigid and soft packaging applications in controlled industrial composting conditions in the lab as well as actual conditions in an industrial composting plant. Results show stark differences between the disintegration of the samples based on mass loss in the lab and in the plant. The 1 mm thick polylactic acid-based blend for rigid packaging experienced much higher disintegration in the lab with 76.4% remaining mass after 4 weeks compared to 97.2% remaining mass after 3 weeks in the industrial composting plant. The 109 µm thick polybutylene succinate-based blend for soft packaging also experienced higher degradation in the lab with 45.4% remaining mass after 4 weeks in the lab compared to 93.8% remaining mass in the industrial composting plant. The shorter high-temperature composting duration in industrial plants as well as the characteristics of their biowaste inputs are potential causes of the large difference. The study highlights the need to better understand the real-world industrial composting conditions and their variations when evaluating composting as a treatment method for biodegradable plastics.

Introduction

The prevalence of plastic waste and micro-plastic in the environment has spurred research and development of alternatives such as biodegradable plastics. Biodegradable plastics include polymers that can be broken down and mineralized by microbial action. They can be produced from both fossil-based and bio-based resources. It is important to note that compostable plastics are a subcategory of biodegradable plastics that would only disintegrate significantly in specific composting conditions, in contrast to general environmental conditions on land or sea. Thus, they need to be kept in controlled closed systems. Commonly available bio-based biodegradable plastics include polylactic acid (PLA) and polybutylene succinate (PBS) (IfBB, 2020).

Industrial compostable products are designed to disintegrate within a reasonable period under industrial composting conditions. The major characteristic of industrial composting is the ability to achieve thermophilic temperatures (Barrena *et al.*, 2014; Sundberg *et al.*, 2004), in the range from 55°C to 75°C. The composting route might be an alternative for the treatment of plastic waste, for example when mechanical recycling is difficult, such as in the case of multilayer packaging (de Mello Soares *et al.*, 2022; Trinh *et al.*, 2021). However, industrial composting primarily aims to treat and stabilize biowaste and produce compost, an agricultural substrate. Thus, the feasibility of the treatment of biodegradable plastics within these plants is not a given.

In Germany, there is no widespread acceptance and treatment of compostable plastics in industrial composting plants (ANS e.V. (ANS) *et al.*, 2019). One of the major issues quoted is the insufficient decomposition of biodegradable plastic products

within the normal operating conditions of the plants. This occurs even with products certified industrially compostable via international standards such as EN 13432. The reason is the wide range of different conditions in which industrial composting operators run their plants, which are sometimes very different from the compostable certification conditions (Di Bartolo *et al.*, 2021; Hann *et al.*, 2020). The disintegration condition in EN 13432 requires that the product disintegrates under industrial composting conditions and leaves behind less than 10% of the material (> 2 mm) by mass after a maximum of 12 weeks. The industrial composting plants in Germany on the other hand, have an active composting duration generally shorter than 12 weeks, usually within a range of 4 to 8 weeks (Stadtreinigung Hamburg, 2019). In addition, there are differences in the composition of the input material fed into the composting process. Some facilities focus on garden waste while others are hybrid biogas and composting plants that predominantly run aerobic composting on the digestate from the anaerobic digestion process.

The behaviour of biodegradable plastics in the composting process has been studied in the literature. However, the duration and conditions of the composting process as well as the design and composition of the plastic vary. Ruggero *et al.*, 2021 simulated an industrial composting process in the lab with 20 days of thermophilic composting (58°C) and 40 days of compost maturation (37°C) with mature compost as the composting medium. They tested a starch and polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT) composite film, a PBAT based film and PLA pressed plate. Other studies focused on the design factors affecting the speed and degree of degradation. For example, micro fibrillated cellulose was found to increase the degradation of PLA composites while cellulose nanocrystals retard degradation (Manzano *et al.*, 2021). In addition to the concentration of fillers, the material thickness was also found to affect the degradation speed of PLA and PBS blends (Tolga *et al.*, 2020). Recently, researchers also studied the effect of treating compostable plastics in composting plants on the composting process itself. Cucina *et al.*, 2021 researched the effects of the high loading of commercially available compostable plastic products in bio-waste (10 wt %) on compost quality. Certified compostable starch-based shopping bags and PLA-based cutlery degraded by 48 wt% and 15 wt% respectively after a combination of a pilot-scale mesophilic dry anaerobic digestion phase (35 days), active composting phase (15 days) and compost maturation phase (40 days). A final concentration of compostable plastic in compost was found to be around 18 wt%.

There is still a need to better understand the factors affecting disintegration rates in actual industrial composting conditions as well as its connection with lab-scale tests. This work thus assessed the degradation rate, measured by mass loss, of two biodegradable plastic prototypes developed for rigid (PLA-based) and soft packaging (PBS-based) respectively within the BIO-PLASTICS EUROPE research project in both lab-scale simulated (DIN EN ISO 20200) and actual industrial

composting conditions. The composting medium was characterized for comparison. The results outlined overall factors affecting the disintegration rate and explored the possible reasons for the differences in the material disintegration rate between the lab-scale and industrial-scale tests.

Methods

Biodegradable plastic test samples

The biodegradable plastic materials tested were a PLA-based biodegradable plastic blend (BPE-RP-PLA) developed for rigid packaging and a PBS-based biodegradable plastic blend (BPE-SP-PBS) developed for soft packaging. Table 1 lists the main characteristics of each blend and the sample thickness used in this study.

The blends are being developed in the framework of the H2020 Research Project [BIO-PLASTICS EUROPE](#). The main filler in BPE-RP-PLA is calcium silicate with an overall ash content of 28.7%. Injection moulded plates of 1 mm thickness were used to represent rigid packaging. BPE-SP-PBS was tested in the form of films around 109 µm thick. The main filler is talc and the blend has an ash content of 9.7%. The thickness tested represents an approximation of the thickness the final products of the target application would have.

Lab-scale industrial composting

The lab-scale test served as a baseline test for ideal industrial composting conditions. The lab-scale industrial composting test was carried out based on ISO 20200 and simulates the thermophilic industrial composting conditions. The composting medium was synthetic bio-waste composed of 40% sawdust, 30% rabbit feed, 10% fresh compost, 5% sucrose, 4% corn seed oil and 1% urea by dry mass. Brief descriptions of the material sources are given in *Extended data* (Chong *et al.*, 2022b). Fresh compost was taken from the Bützberg Biogas and Composting plant as inoculum. The water content was adjusted to 55 wt% at the start of the experiment.

For each reactor system, 1.1 kg of composting medium was mixed with around 10 g of plastic sample (~1 wt% sample loading) in polypropylene boxes with lids (dimensions 34 cm X 20 cm X 12.5 cm). The initial mass of the dry plastic samples was weighed and recorded before adding to the reactor. Each box had two holes of 5 mm diameter on the sides for aeration.

Table 1. The main characteristics of the biodegradable plastic blends tested.

Blend code	BPE-RP-PLA	BPE-SP-PBS
Target application	Rigid packaging	Soft packaging
Base polymer	PLA	PBS
Main Filler	Calcium Silicate	Talc
Ash content	28.7%	9.7%
Sample thickness	1 mm plates	109±9 µm films

For BPE-RP-PLA, samples cut into 2.5 cm X 2.5 cm pieces were used following ISO 20200. For BPE-SP-PBS films, individual pieces cut into 5 cm X 5 cm pieces were used instead to make them more manageable. The reactor systems were placed in a convection oven maintained at a temperature of 58°C throughout the experiment, simulating the thermophilic composting phase.

The reactor contents were weighed and the moisture content was replenished based on the schedule defined in ISO 20200 to ensure sufficient moisture content. In addition, the contents were gently mixed if instructed. The mass loss of the plastic samples was measured after 4, 8 and 12 weeks. Triplicate reactor systems were set up for each time point. In addition, 3 reactor systems without the plastic samples were set up as control.

At the end of the defined composting duration, the process was stopped by drying the reactor contents in the oven after removing the lid until constant weight is achieved. The mass before and after drying was used to estimate the final moisture content. The remaining plastic samples were recovered by sieving the reactor contents with a 2 mm mesh analytical sieve (RETSCH GmbH, Haan, Germany). The sample pieces were cleaned gently under running water and oven-dried at 58°C before final weighing. The initial and final weight was used to calculate the remaining mass using Equation 1. The remaining dried compost medium was then milled into powder and further analysed for pH, C/N ratio and volatile organic solids content using standard methods. Further details of the materials and methodologies used are described in *Extended data* (Chong *et al.*, 2022b).

$$\text{Remaining mass (\%)} = \frac{\text{Mass}_{\text{final} > 2\text{mm}}}{\text{Mass}_{\text{initial}}} \times 100\% \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

On-field industrial composting test

To study the behaviour of biodegradable plastic samples in real-world conditions, the samples were subjected to industrial composting in the Bützberg Biogas and Composting Plant located in Tangstedt, Germany. The plant receives separately collected bio-waste from households in the region. Before undergoing biological treatment, the waste was shredded (< 8 cm), sieved and sent through magnetic separation to remove impurities. The plant then ran a dry anaerobic digestion process on the pre-treated biowaste for biogas production followed by in-vessel composting of the digestate material after anaerobic digestion. Hybrid fermentation chambers 24 m x 5 m x 4.5 m were used for the anaerobic digestion phase. For this study, the composting phase was carried out in the hybrid fermenters with aeration after the anaerobic digestion phase. The industrial composting outputs were finally sieved to produce compost for sale.

For each test instance, around 10 g of sample and 1 kg of fresh digestate material from anaerobic digestion were mixed and placed into polyethylene terephthalate (PET) mesh bags

with a mesh size of 1-2 mm. The initial mass of the dry plastic samples was weighed and recorded before adding to the PET mesh bags. This enabled recovery of sample pieces > 2mm at the end of the experiment for mass loss measurements. For BPE-RP-PLA, pieces of 5cm X 5cm were used according to DIN EN ISO 16929, the standard for pilot scale disintegration tests. For BPE-SP-PBS, individual film pieces of 10 cm X 10 cm were used. The bags were then sealed and placed into specially constructed metal sample cages (25 cm X 25 cm X 50 cm) with stainless steel grates with a mesh size of 10-12 mm. The cages were filled with more digestate material and placed in the middle of the composting pile together with two probes for temperature measurements. The experimental setup is shown in Figure 1. Each biodegradable plastic blend was tested in duplicate.

The exposure was carried out for three weeks, which is the composting duration for this batch of digestate material. After the first and second week, the composting pile was mixed in which the entire mass was transferred via a wheel loader from one hybrid fermentation chamber to another. In these phases, the sample cages were extracted, gently rotated to encourage mixing and reinserted into the composting pile. At the end of the

composting process, the sample bags were extracted and dried in an oven at 105°C until constant weight. The plastic pieces were then extracted through sieving at 2 mm, washed and oven-dried at 58°C before final weighing. The initial and final weight was used to calculate the remaining mass using Equation 1. Samples of the composting medium were taken at the start and end of the experiment, oven-dried at 105°C to measure moisture content. The biomass was then ground into powder for further characterization of pH, C/N ratio and volatile solids content using standard methods described in *Extended data* (Chong *et al.*, 2022b).

Results and discussion

Disintegration rate in lab-scale industrial composting

Figure 2 shows the average measured remaining mass of the samples larger than the 2 mm limit as defined by ISO 20200, as well as the standard deviation of the triplicate measurements. The remaining mass of BPE-SP-PBS is 45.4%, 10.9% and 0.3% by weeks 4, 8 and 12 respectively. BPE-SP-PBS in the current form will thus fulfil the 90% disintegration condition (10% remaining mass) set by ISO 20200 after a little over 8 weeks. In contrast, 55.7% of BPE-RP-PLA remained larger than 2 mm after 12 weeks with only a small difference between week 8 and

Figure 1. Experimental setup in the industrial composting plant. (a) biodegradable plastic samples with digestate material in sample nets. (b) sample nets in a metal cage. (c) position of the cages in the composting pile.

Figure 2. The remaining mass of samples in the lab-scale simulated industrial composting.

week 12. BPE-RP-PLA in its current form thus does not fulfil the 90% disintegration condition. For both materials, the decrease in volatile solids of the composting medium (denoted R in ISO 20200) met the minimum requirement of the standard set at 30% from week 4 onward. The R-values and mass loss data are tabulated in *Underlying data* (Chong *et al.*, 2022a). The large standard deviation at week 4 for BPE-SP-PBS can be attributed to uneven contact of the films with the composting environment, as it was observed that the pieces above the composting medium experienced little disintegration. After week 4, the pieces reduced in size and thus could be evenly distributed within the composting medium. The deviations in mass loss of the other time points were within the 20% limit set by ISO 20200.

The lab-scale results indicate that BPE-SP-PBS of a thickness $\leq 109 \mu\text{m}$ would meet the disintegration requirement in an industrial composting plant as long as the residence time of thermophilic composting is longer than 8 weeks. On the other hand, BPE-RP-PLA in its current form would not disintegrate sufficiently in industrial composting plants with an active thermophilic composting time of fewer than 12 weeks.

Disintegration rate in an industrial composting plant

The degradation rates after exposure in an industrial composting plant are shown in Figure 3. The tests were conducted in duplicates. After 3 weeks of exposure to industrial composting of the digestate material from anaerobic digestion, the samples experienced only minor mass losses. For BPE-RP-PLA, the remaining mass was 97.2% and 99.5%. BPE-SP-PBS samples experienced slightly higher mass loss with 94.0% and 93.8% remaining mass.

The resulting mass loss after 3 weeks of industrial composting is much lower compared to the results from the lab-scale tests at week 4. This is most likely due to the differences in the composting medium and conditions, which are further discussed in Section 3.3. Similar to the lab-scale test, BPE-SP-PBS experienced faster disintegration in general when compared to BPE-RP-PLA.

Although the reduction in mass is not significant, BPE-RP-PLA had significant visual changes including yellowing and unevenness on the surface. BPE-SP-PBS also experienced yellowing and warping with noticeable holes. Figure 4 depicts the material after industrial composting, cleaning and drying. In addition, all samples became more brittle and prone to fragmentation. This signifies a structural degradation of the polymer matrix.

The results indicate that the blends in the current form are not suitable for treatment in the industrial composting process where the test was carried out. Although degradation of the material was observed, the disintegration rate is very low within the active composting duration of the plant.

Differences in composting conditions between the lab-scale and on-field tests

The lab-scale test based on ISO 20200 simulates a controlled thermophilic environment with a well-defined composting medium with small particle sizes (95% $< 1 \text{ cm}$). On the other hand, the digestate material with which industrial composting was carried out had a larger and broader particle size distribution (shredded to $\leq 8 \text{ cm}$). The composition would also change seasonally depending on separately collected biowaste from households. The measured pH, moisture content, volatile solids content and C/N ratio of the composting medium in both tests are listed in Table 2. The standard deviation of the total volatile solid measurements reflects the heterogeneity of the on-field composting medium, which had higher variation compared to the composting medium used in the lab.

The average volatile solid content of the lab-scale composting medium was higher compared to the on-field medium. Since the on-field medium stems from biowaste, it is expected that the inorganic content, i.e. sand and dust, will be higher due to the mixed collection of food and garden waste. The pH of the lab-scale composting medium was slightly acidic while the pH of the on-field medium was neutral; both in the accepted range

Figure 3. The remaining mass of samples after industrial composting on-field.

Figure 4. Samples before and after on-field industrial composting. (a,b) BPE-RP-PLA. (c,d) BPE-SP-PBS.

Table 2. Lab-scale and on-field composting medium at the start of the experiment.

Test type	Lab-scale	On-field
Brief description	A well-defined mix of materials based on ISO 20200.	A mixture of food and garden waste after dry anaerobic digestion. The composition depends on separately collected biowaste in the region.
Particle size	95% < 1cm	≤ 8cm
Total dry solids¹	45.0% (Start) ⁴ 26.6%±1.0% (End) ⁵	37.1%±5.0% (Start) 47.6%±1.9% (End)
Total volatile solids²	90.6%±0.6%	37.8%±2.6%
pH³	5.8±0.1	6.9±0.1
C/N ratio³	33±2	19±1

¹ Based on wet weight. ² Based on total dry solids. ³ Measured on oven-dried and ground samples. ⁴ The moisture content was adjusted at the start of the experiment and thus not measured. ⁵ After four weeks of composting BPE-SP-PBS.

for bacteria and fungi (Chen *et al.*, 2011). The C/N ratios of the lab-scale and on-field composting medium were close to the optimal for composting, quoted at 25 to 30 (Kumar *et al.*, 2010). Generally, it could be argued that the lab-scale composting medium with its smaller particle sizes and higher organic solids content is more conducive to disintegration as it facilitates a better sample-medium contact and higher biological activity. This could explain the better disintegration rates of the samples in the lab. In addition, the composting medium in the lab-scale test is mixed more frequently (based on the schedule in ISO 20200) compared to the on-field composting medium (once a week).

Moreover, the temperature profiles of the processes differed. In the lab-scale experiment, the temperature was kept constant at 58°C via a convection oven. In contrast, the temperature of the on-field composting medium depended on self-heating and went through multiple cycles corresponding to the mixing schedules. The profiles of the temperature measured by the two probes are shown in Figure 5. The two dips in the middle correspond to the mixing phase, where the composting chambers are open and the composting medium is transferred from one chamber to another to facilitate mixing. The temperature ranged from 40°C to 80°C with an approximate median of 60°C. In both cases, the temperatures were well within the thermophilic range. Indicated by the measurements at the start and end of the experiments, the lab-scale test experienced wetter environments compared to the on-field test as a result of the methodology laid out in ISO 20200. A wetter environment might facilitate better disintegration of PLA and PBS. The disintegration of PLA initially relies on chemical hydrolysis to break down long-chain polymers (Mochizuki & Hiram, 1997) and thus benefits from higher humidity (Karamanlioglu *et al.*, 2017). The degradation of

PBS relies on enzymatic activity on the surface (Su *et al.*, 2019) as well as hydrolysis (Muthuraj *et al.*, 2015) and thus would also benefit from increased moisture.

Feasibility of treating compostable plastic packaging in industrial composting plants

This study indicates that both blends in their current form do not meet the 90% disintegration requirement for compostable packaging according to EN 13432 after exposure to the process at the Bützberg plant. The disintegration rates might be higher if the samples are not contained in sample nets and metal cages and thus more susceptible to mechanical stresses during the composting process, i.e. during mixing. However, due to the very low disintegration rates observed, i.e. all samples were lower than 7%, it is unlikely that the disintegration rates will improve above the 90% disintegration rate required by ISO 20200 and EN 13432.

The disintegration of BPE-SP-PBS in other industrial composting plants might meet the requirement if the thermophilic composting phase is longer than 8 weeks with fresh biowaste as the composting medium, as indicated by the lab-scale test results. However, the thermophilic composting phase of most industrial processes does not exceed 3 weeks (Ruggero *et al.*, 2021). For BPE-RP-PLA, the thermophilic composting phase would need to be longer than 12 weeks to achieve sufficient degradation according to the lab-scale test results.

The conditions defined for certified compostable packaging, for example, those with their disintegration tested according to the pilot-scale disintegration test according to ISO 16929, are 4 weeks of composting above 55°C, 4 weeks of composting above 50°C and 4 weeks of composting below 45°C using fresh

Figure 5. The temperature profile of the on-field industrial composting (Bützberg Biogas and Composting Plant, 2021).

biowaste as inputs. These conditions also deviate from those in Bützberg and similar plants, and thus the disintegration rate is expected to be low.

An important determining factor for disintegration is the shape and form of the biodegradable packaging articles, i.e. Tolga *et al.*, (2020) found that the degree of disintegration linearly correlated with the thickness of PLA/PBS blends. Especially for rigid packaging, the thickness presents an extra obstacle. Extra pre-processing steps, i.e. shredding, would likely be needed if the disintegration of biodegradable plastics in industrial composting plants is to be increased. Further research on the effects of differing composting medium compositions, organic solids content, and particle size distributions are needed to understand the scenarios in which the disintegration rates will meet requirements.

It should be noted that the disintegration rate with a scope above 2 mm is not sufficient when considering the feasibility of treating compostable plastic in industrial composting plants. The behaviour and ultimate biodegradation of the smaller compostable plastic particles in the environments in which they might enter, i.e. agricultural or garden soil, as well as their toxicity, should be determined (Fojt *et al.*, 2020; Karamanlioglu & Alkan, 2020). Lastly, integration with the wider waste management system needs to be considered. For one, the motivation of the industrial composting plants to sanitize biowaste and produce compost might not align with the treatment of compostable plastics, which might complicate the process without added benefit to the plant operator.

Conclusion

Heeding the resistance from some waste management authorities to treat compostable plastics in composting plants, the behaviour of biodegradable and compostable plastics under actual industrial composting conditions should be thoroughly examined to assess their environmental impact. Therefore, this study investigated the disintegration rate of a PLA blend and a PBS blend designed for rigid and soft packaging respectively under simulated lab-scale and on-site industrial composting conditions. While under simulated industrial conditions according to ISO 20200, the remaining mass of BPE-RP-PLA and BPE-SP-PBS samples were 76.4% and 45.4% respectively after 4 weeks and 55.7% and 0.3% after 12 weeks. On the contrary, the degree of disintegration under on-site conditions was significantly lower with remaining masses at least 97.2% for the BPE-RP-PLA samples and 93.8% for the BPE-SP-PBS samples after 3 weeks of thermophilic composting. Apart from the thickness of the plastic samples and the duration of the thermophilic composting phase, composting conditions such as substrate composition and particle size could be major influencing factors.

Although BPE-SP-PBS samples in their current thickness almost disintegrated entirely after 12 weeks, a minimum thermophilic composting duration of 8 weeks would be necessary to reach the 90% disintegration (10% remaining mass) required by EN 13432, which exceeds the thermophilic phase of most composting plants. Biological waste treatment plants including

composting plants are generally designed to treat and sanitize biological waste and are not optimized to treat compostable plastics, especially concerning the retention time. Henceforth, realistic certification requirements that reflect differing retention times and substrate composition which occur in real-life applications should be considered. Furthermore, systemic integration considering the biowaste value chain and the motivations of industrial composting plants is critical.

Data availability

Underlying data

B2Share: Underlying data_Lab-scale and on-field industrial composting of biodegradable plastic blends for packaging_Chong *et al.*, 2022

<http://doi.org/10.23728/b2share.96956d1bae7d40cb80e0c6b4dfa0b30f> (Chong *et al.*, 2022a)

This project contains the following underlying data:

- CN ratio_Industrial test.xlsx
- CN ratio_lab-scale.xlsx
- Data list.docx
- Moisture content.xlsx
- pH.xlsx
- Remaining mass industrial test.xlsx
- Remaining mass lab-scale_BPE-RP-PLA.xlsx
- Remaining mass lab-scale_BPE-SP-PBS.xlsx
- R value lab-scale test reactors_BPE-RP-PLA.xlsx
- R value lab-scale test reactors_BPE-SP-PBS.xlsx
- Total volatile solids.xlsx

Extended data

B2Share: Extended data_Lab-scale and on-field industrial composting of biodegradable plastic blends for packaging_Chong *et al.*, 2022

<http://doi.org/10.23728/b2share.5356b112d6bd424aa79b10d397ee1b81> (Chong *et al.*, 2022b)

This project contains the following extended data:

- Extended data_Methodology.docx

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) (CC-BY 4.0).

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Douglas G. Hayes

Department of Biosystems Engineering & Soil Science, University of Tennessee, Knoxville, TN, USA

I find this manuscript to be publishable after addressing minor revisions. The experimental work is reliable and was performed correctly, per ISO 16929 and 20200 standardized testing conditions for measuring disintegration. The interpretation of the data is mostly correct, in my opinion. However, there are a few places where I believe interpretation should be reconsidered. First, one must be careful on extending results achieved using standardized tests and specifications achieved per a standard to actual performance in an industrial composting facility. As the authors likely know, composting is truly an art and its performance can be affected by several different parameters. Second, biodegradation is directly controlled by the surface area per volume of the plastic material. This is relevant in two contexts: A) The PLA test material has a 10-fold higher thickness compared to PBS, which will lead to a lower biodegradation rate for PLA, and B) The mesh bags used in the study will likely introduce a resistance to mass transfer of nutrients and gases across the mesh bag matrix. In addition, the presentation can be improved in a few places in the manuscript.

Regarding the mass transfer inhibition of biodegradation (disintegration) caused by the mesh bag, I would recommend performing a side-by-side laboratory test of a standard plastic testing material (e.g., a thin PLA film) directly in compost vs in a mesh bag placed in compost. Such an experiment does not need to be carried out for the full duration of the experiments described in your paper; perhaps a few weeks would suffice. We did this: H.Y. Sintim, et al., 2019¹ (within Supplementary Materials) and found for our systems that the mesh bags significantly slowed the biodegradation rate in compost.

My specific comments are given below.

1. Introduction, first paragraph: I would recommend defining “disintegration” and “composting” carefully. EN 13432 or one of the ISO disintegration testing methods should have these definitions. I disagree with to the use of “only” (“..would ONLY disintegrate significantly..”). A substance’s ability to readily biodegrade under composting conditions does not preclude the substance’s ability to readily biodegrade in a different environment (e.g., soil, activated sludge, or seawater).

2. Introduction, 3rd paragraph: "The disintegration condition in EN 13432 .. after a maximum of 12 weeks". This sentence needs to be qualified: "..according to the _____ standardized testing conditions"
3. More information should be provided on the properties of the polymeric materials, such as weight-averaged molecular weight, glass transition temperature, apparent density (grams per square meter), etc.
4. Methods, Lab-scale composting. Were the composting ingredients or the compost itself treated with sieving prior to the addition of plastic?
5. Results and Discussion, first paragraph, "current form does not fulfil the 90% disintegration conditions" needs a qualifier, such as "specified in EN 13432"
6. Please consider merging Figs 2 and 3. The data of Fig 3 can be easily incorporated as datapoints into Fig 2. (Note, for the current Fig 3, y-axis numbers should have the zeroes to the right of the decimal place removed and the caption should indicate the duration.)
7. Fig 2: Do error bars represent standard deviation, standard error, or something else? Please elaborate (e.g., in the figure caption).
8. Results and discussion, "disintegration rate in an industrial composting plant" subsection, bottommost paragraph. This paragraph needs revision. First, as mentioned above, it is likely that the mesh bag promoted mass transfer limitations on the biodegradation reaction. Second, I believe that the non-compliance of PLA to the EN 13432 standards is at least partially attributable to the high, 1 mm, thickness of the films and perhaps the high content of calcium silicate nanofiller may play a role as inhibitor of biodegradation. Are the composting conditions and medium a factor? I find that the inclusion of a positive control into the experimental design, such as a standard plastic material (e.g., a thinner PLA film) improves in the interpretation of the results, although I realize that the ISO standardized tests for disintegration do not directly call for it. Please consider revising the discussion in this paragraph.
9. Feasibility of treating compostable plastic packaging .. " subsection, first paragraph, "do not meet the 90% disintegration requirement". I find this paragraph requires revision, noting first that the PBS material does appear to meet the requirement under laboratory conditions, per Fig 2. The assessment given in this paragraph needs to take into account the high thickness of the PLA film and the mass transfer limitations imposed by the mesh bag for the data of Fig 3 (as discussed above)

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Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Biobased and biodegradable agricultural plastics, micro- and nanoplastics, colloidal systems

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 25 Aug 2023

Zhi Kai Chong

The authors would like to thank Douglas G. Hayes for the detailed review and constructive comments. The table below summarises the authors' comments and enhancements made to the new version in response to the review. Review Section Authors' replies and comments I find this manuscript to be publishable after addressing minor revisions. The experimental work is reliable and was performed correctly, per ISO 16929 and 20200 standardized testing conditions for measuring disintegration. The interpretation of the data is mostly correct, in my opinion. However, there are a few places where I believe interpretation should be reconsidered. First, one must be careful on extending results achieved using standardized tests and specifications achieved per a standard to actual performance in an industrial composting facility. As the authors likely know, composting is truly an art and its performance can be affected by several different parameters. Second, biodegradation is directly controlled by the surface area per volume of the plastic material. This is relevant in two contexts: A) The PLA test material has a 10-fold higher thickness compared to PBS, which will lead to a lower biodegradation rate for PLA, and B) The mesh bags used in the study will likely introduce a resistance to mass transfer of nutrients and gases across the mesh bag matrix. In addition, the presentation can be improved in a few places in the manuscript. The authors agree that extending results from standardized test to industrial

composting plant is highly problematic. The difference between our results in the lab compared to the industrial composting plant is evidence of that. The possible reasons for the difference in disintegration rates were enhanced in the section "Differences in composting conditions between the lab-scale and on-field tests", paragraph 2 to 4. The specific surface area of the samples were added in Table 1. In addition, the influence of the specific surface area on the results comparing the film and plate samples were added in the Section "Disintegration rate in lab-scale industrial composting", paragraph 2 and 3. A discussion of the potential effect of the mesh bags was also included in the section "Disintegration rate in an industrial composting plant", paragraph 5. Regarding the mass transfer inhibition of biodegradation (disintegration) caused by the mesh bag, I would recommend performing a side-by-side laboratory test of a standard plastic testing material (e.g., a thin PLA film) directly in compost vs in a mesh bag placed in compost. Such an experiment does not need to be carried out for the full duration of the experiments described in your paper; perhaps a few weeks would suffice. We did this: H.Y. Sintim, et al., 20191 (within Supplementary Materials) and found for our systems that the mesh bags significantly slowed the biodegradation rate in compost. Thank you for the helpful comments. A discussion of the potential effect of the mesh bags was added to the section "Disintegration rate in an industrial composting plant", paragraph 5. In addition, the potential effect of using mesh bags coupled with the heterogeneity of the substrate is mentioned in the section "Differences in composting conditions between the lab-scale and on-field tests", paragraph 2. Due to the presence of 1 kg of organic waste directly in contact with the samples in the on-field test, we believe the risk of reduced contact is minimal. However, the substrate within the mesh bags might have lower disintegration rates considering reduced mixing with the rest of the compost pile.

1. Introduction, first paragraph: I would recommend defining "disintegration" and "composting" carefully. EN 13432 or one of the ISO disintegration testing methods should have these definitions. I disagree with to the use of "only" ("..would ONLY disintegrate significantly.."). A substance's ability to readily biodegrade under composting conditions does not preclude the substance's ability to readily biodegrade in a different environment (e.g., soil, activated sludge, or seawater). Definitions for biodegradation and disintegration were added in section "Introduction", paragraph 1. In addition, a sentence rephrased to "Compostable plastics are a subcategory of biodegradable plastics that disintegrate significantly in specific composting conditions, but not necessarily in general environmental conditions on land or sea."

2. Introduction, 3rd paragraph: "The disintegration condition in EN 13432 .. after a maximum of 12 weeks". This sentence needs to be qualified: "..according to the _____ standardized testing conditions" Qualifier added "in a "controlled pilot-scale test" or in industrial composting plants"

3. More information should be provided on the properties of the polymeric materials, such as weight-averaged molecular weight, glass transition temperature, apparent density (grams per square meter), etc. The weight average molecular weight, glass transition temperature and specific surface area (square centimeter per gram) were added to Table 1. Due to the lack of data, the average molecular weight of BPE-SP-PBS is not available. The glass transition temperature typical for PBS was extracted from literature. The discussion in paragraph 2 and 3 of the section "Disintegration rate in lab-scale industrial composting" was also enhanced using the added information.

4. Methods, Lab-scale composting. Were the composting ingredients or the compost itself treated with sieving prior to the addition of plastic? The substrate mix was not treated with sieving prior to the test. This is because the components were based on ISO 20200 and

were sourced from homogeneous sources. From our sieving analysis, at least 95% of the substrate had a particle size less than 1 cm. The compost itself was sieved in the production line of the composting plant. On visual inspection, we did not identify plastic particles that may affect the results of the experiment.

5. Results and Discussion, first paragraph, "current form does not fulfil the 90% disintegration conditions" needs a qualifier, such as "specified in EN 13432" Qualifier added "based on ISO 20200".

6. Please consider merging Figs 2 and 3. The data of Fig 3 can be easily incorporated as datapoints into Fig 2. (Note, for the current Fig 3, y-axis numbers should have the zeroes to the right of the decimal place removed and the caption should indicate the duration.) That is a good point, thank you. We added additional data for a lab-scale test for 3 weeks to Figure 3 reflecting the duration as well as material dimensions used in the on-field test in the industrial composting plant. We also edited the figure as suggested. Due to the differing dimensions of the samples used for the 1st lab-scale test, we prefer to keep the figures separate.

7. Fig 2: Do error bars represent standard deviation, standard error, or something else? Please elaborate (e.g., in the figure caption). Thank you for the reminder, the error bars represent the standard deviation. All figure captions were updated.

8. Results and discussion, "disintegration rate in an industrial composting plant" subsection, bottommost paragraph. This paragraph needs revision. First, as mentioned above, it is likely that the mesh bag promoted mass transfer limitations on the biodegradation reaction. Second, I believe that the non-compliance of PLA to the EN 13432 standards is at least partially attributable to the high, 1 mm, thickness of the films and perhaps the high content of calcium silicate nanofiller may play a role as inhibitor of biodegradation. Are the composting conditions and medium a factor? I find that the inclusion of a positive control into the experimental design, such as a standard plastic material (e.g., a thinner PLA film) improves in the interpretation of the results, although I realize that the ISO standardized tests for disintegration do not directly call for it. Please consider revising the discussion in this paragraph. We tested the blends in the current form as they were prototypes of soft as well as rigid packaging respectively. We acknowledge the role of the blend composition and shape on the results. We appended a note to that paragraph and discussed the potential effects of the sample thickness in the Section "Feasibility of treating compostable plastic packaging in industrial composting plants", paragraph 4. A comparison considering the filler content was added in the section "Disintegration rate in lab-scale industrial composting", paragraph 3.

9. Feasibility of treating compostable plastic packaging .. " subsection, first paragraph, "do not meet the 90% disintegration requirement". I find this paragraph requires revision, noting first that the PBS material does appear to meet the requirement under laboratory conditions, per Fig 2. The assessment given in this paragraph needs to take into account the high thickness of the PLA film and the mass transfer limitations imposed by the mesh bag for the data of Fig 3 (as discussed above) We understand and appreciate the comment. The section was revised to highlight the potential effects of sample thickness in paragraph 4. In addition, the wording was enhanced in order to make clear that the results do not represent an absolute negative evaluation but point out the many factors that needs to be additionally considered. A discussion of the potential effect of the mesh bags was also added to the section "Disintegration rate in an industrial composting plant", paragraph 5 and reiterated in this section.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 10 October 2022

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.16095.r29962>

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Mehlika Karamanlioglu

Faculty of Engineering and Architecture, Department of Biomedical Engineering, Istanbul Gelisim University, İstanbul, Turkey

This study compares degradation rate of compostable blends under lab conditions and in industrial composting plants. For this purpose, two different packaging blends, i.e., polylactic acid (PLA) based rigid packaging and polybutylene succinate (PBS) based soft packaging, were used. Lab-scale tests were carried out according to ISO 20200 and samples were recovered after 4, 8 and 12 weeks. On field test lasted for 3 weeks. Both were under thermophilic conditions. Mass loss of samples was calculated to determine degradation.

1. In order to make an accurate comparison of degradation rates between lab conditions and on field conditions, sample recovery time should be the same. Samples were recovered earlier from the industrial composting site compared to lab scale tests. PLA quickly degrades under thermophilic conditions, above its glass transition temperature (T_g), therefore one more week in an industrial composting site under thermophilic conditions would affect the results. It is mentioned that thermophilic phase does not exceed 3 weeks in industrial processes, therefore, samples could have been recovered during the 3rd week of incubation under lab conditions as well so that an accurate comparison between lab conditions and on field conditions can be conducted. Otherwise, there is a duration factor under thermophilic conditions which cannot be omitted. Actually, for better comparison and for research purposes, on field samples should have been collected after 4, 8 and 12 weeks as well.
2. Different dimensions of each blend are used for each degradation environment. To make an accurate comparison of degradation rates between lab conditions and on field conditions, sample dimensions should be the same.
3. Apart from mass change, another degradation assessment method is highly recommended such as a Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC). Cleaning the debris without compromising the sample is not easy which may lead to inaccurate results. For instance, molecular weights can be compared after 3 weeks of incubation in both conditions.
4. In methods, more detail about the plastics used in this study should also be given in this study as well (Table 1). The information would help to explain the degradation rate of the plastics. For instance, PLA properties such as its molecular weight and T_g greatly affect its degradation rate.
5. A brief comparison between the difference in degradation rate of PLA and PBS can be discussed.

6. Page 3: Please add the reference after these sentences: 'Certified compostable starch-based shopping bags and PLA-based cutlery degraded by 48 wt% and 15 wt% respectively after a combination of a pilot-scale mesophilic dry anaerobic digestion phase (35 days), active composting phase (15 days) and compost maturation phase (40 days). A final concentration of compostable plastic in compost was found to be around 18 wt%.'
7. Page 6: Section 3.3 is mentioned but the section number cannot be found in the main text.
8. Page 8: 'However, due to the very low disintegration rates observed, i.e. all samples were lower than 7%, it is unlikely that the disintegration rates will improve above the 90% disintegration rate required by ISO 20200 and EN 13432.' The assumption drawn here is highly speculative since there is not enough data. No rate is determined, no interpolation is calculated and there are no mathematical models, etc. It is based on only one time sampling at the end of 3rd week. Sampling should have been carried out each week and for a longer period of time to make an estimation.
9. Page 9: Grammar should be revised in the following sentence: 'Further research on the effects of differing composting medium compositions, organic solids content, and particle size distributions are needed to understand the scenarios in which the disintegration rates will meet requirements'.
10. Page 10: In conclusion part, moisture content is another factor that affects degradation. Also, microorganisms and their diversity affect degradation in compost. They should be mentioned.
11. In conclusion part (Page 1), comparing 3rd week in the field and 4th week in the lab is not feasible. Why do the authors think the main reason of different degradation rate is the 'composition of the composting substrate'. The evidence should be provided.

In the same part, the last sentence should be more clearly presented.
12. In general, this research can be a great contribution to the literature and to the process of industrial composting of certain plastics. The research is clearly and accurately presented but some more fundamental and also recent papers should be cited to better explain the degradation of the plastics used in this study. Main factors that contribute to their degradation should be presented from the literature.

In literature, PBS and even high molecular PLA degrades fast under thermophilic conditions in compost (Kale et al., 2007). However, in this study less than 5% of PLA blend was degraded in 3 weeks. Weren't samples in full contact with the compost due to mesh bags? Weren't they buried in the pile? The reasons of slower degradation rate in this study should be discussed more in detail and compared with literature. Is there any other study that contained samples in mesh bags, how long did it take for them to degrade?

A significant revision and some additional data mentioned above are necessary for this study.

References

1. Kale G, Auras R, Singh S: Comparison of the degradability of poly(lactide) packages in

composting and ambient exposure conditions. *Packaging Technology and Science*. 2007; **20** (1): 49-70 [Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Biotechnology, biopolymers, environmental degradation of plastics.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 25 Aug 2023

Zhi Kai Chong

The authors would like to thank Mehlika Karamanlioglu for the detailed review and constructive comments. The table below summarises the authors' comments and enhancements made to the new version in response to the review. Review Section Authors' replies and comments (1) In order to make an accurate comparison of degradation rates between lab conditions and on field conditions, sample recovery time should be the same. Samples were recovered earlier from the industrial composting site compared to lab scale tests. PLA quickly degrades under thermophilic conditions, above its glass transition temperature (Tg), therefore one more week in an industrial composting site under thermophilic conditions would affect the results. It is mentioned that thermophilic phase does not exceed 3 weeks in industrial processes, therefore, samples could have been recovered during the 3rd week of incubation under lab conditions as well so that an accurate comparison between lab conditions and on field conditions can be conducted. Otherwise, there is a duration factor under thermophilic conditions which cannot be omitted. Actually, for better comparison and for research purposes, on field samples should

have been collected after 4, 8 and 12 weeks as well. (2) Different dimensions of each blend are used for each degradation environment. To make an accurate comparison of degradation rates between lab conditions and on field conditions, sample dimensions should be the same. The lab-scale test was done mainly to check the disintegration potential of the samples in a controlled environment. However, we completely understand and agree with the downside to the duration mismatch for comparison between the two types of tests. To facilitate a better comparison between the industrial-scale and lab-scale tests, an additional test in the lab based on ISO 20200 was conducted with a duration of 3 weeks to match the duration exposed in the industrial plant and added to the new version of the paper. Sample dimensions identical to those in the field test were used. The results and discussions were reevaluated based on the new data and described in the Section "Disintegration rate in an industrial composting plant". It was observed that the lab-scale test according to ISO 20200 showed higher degradation and disintegration after 3 weeks. Conducting an experiment in the industrial plant for 4, 8 and 12 weeks was unfortunately not currently possible due to the high complexity of integrating the sample exposure method into the workflow of the plant. This is a potential point for future research. (3) Apart from mass change, another degradation assessment method is highly recommended such as a Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC). Cleaning the debris without compromising the sample is not easy which may lead to inaccurate results. For instance, molecular weights can be compared after 3 weeks of incubation in both conditions. That is a really good point, however, a GPC test is not currently possible from our side. In our paper, the main measure of degradation is the mass loss with a cutoff threshold > 2 mm and we based our discussion on this measure. (4) In methods, more detail about the plastics used in this study should also be given in this study as well (Table 1). The information would help to explain the degradation rate of the plastics. For instance, PLA properties such as its molecular weight and Tg greatly affect its degradation rate. The average molecular weight was added for BPE-RP-PLA whilst the glass transition temperature was added for both BPE-RP-PLA and BPE-SP-PBS in Table 1. The average molecular weight for BPE-SP-PBS is not available. In addition, the effect of glass transition temperature on degradation was added to paragraph 7 of the Section "Introduction". The starting molecular weight of BPE-RP-PLA (237000 g/mol) was similar to a study (Kale et al., 2007) with 230000 g/mol, which reported complete disintegration within 30 days in a 65°C environment. However, the blend composition is different and the thickness was not mentioned in the study. Thus, making a direct comparison is not possible. In our study, the samples disintegrated significantly in the lab-scale (58 °C). On the other hand, degradation was observed with minor disintegration (mass loss) after the on-field test (64 °C). We explained possible reasons for this discrepancy in the Section "Differences in composting conditions between the lab-scale and on-field tests". (5) A brief comparison between the difference in degradation rate of PLA and PBS can be discussed. Thank you for the comment, a section discussing the contributing factors to the differing disintegration rate of BPE-RP-PLA and BPE-SP-PBS was added in Paragraph 3 of the Section "Disintegration rate in lab-scale industrial composting". (6) Page 3: Please add the reference after these sentences: 'Certified compostable starch-based shopping bags and PLA-based cutlery degraded by 48 wt% and 15 wt% respectively after a combination of a pilot-scale mesophilic dry anaerobic digestion phase (35 days), active composting phase (15 days) and compost maturation phase (40 days). A final concentration of compostable plastic in compost was found to be around 18 wt%.' The sentence was rephrased mentioning the source, which was (Cucina et al., 2021). (7) Page 6: Section 3.3 is mentioned but the section

number cannot be found in the main text. "Section 3.3" was corrected to "Differences in composting conditions between the lab-scale and on-field tests". (8) Page 8: 'However, due to the very low disintegration rates observed, i.e. all samples were lower than 7%, it is unlikely that the disintegration rates will improve above the 90% disintegration rate required by ISO 20200 and EN 13432.' The assumption drawn here is highly speculative since there is not enough data. No rate is determined, no interpolation is calculated and there are no mathematical models, etc. It is based on only one time sampling at the end of 3rd week. Sampling should have been carried out each week and for a longer period of time to make an estimation. The statement was removed. (9) Page 9: Grammar should be revised in the following sentence: 'Further research on the effects of differing composting medium compositions, organic solids content, and particle size distributions are needed to understand the scenarios in which the disintegration rates will meet requirements'. The statement was rephrased to "However, research on the effects of differing substrate composition, particle size distribution and other parameters such as total volatile solids is lacking and important to understand the requirements for sufficient disintegration in actual plants as well as to understand the potential differences between plants." (10) Page 10: In conclusion part, moisture content is another factor that affects degradation. Also, microorganisms and their diversity affect degradation in compost. They should be mentioned. Thank you for the comment, the factors were mentioned as suggested and added in the conclusion. (11) In conclusion part (Page 1), comparing 3rd week in the field and 4th week in the lab is not feasible. Why do the authors think the main reason of different degradation rate is the 'composition of the composting substrate'. The evidence should be provided. In the same part, the last sentence should be more clearly presented. The conclusion was revised and further elaborated addressing the comment with the new data from 3 weeks composting in the lab-scale: "Based on the data in this study, the abiotic conditions such temperature, moisture content and pH in the lab-scale was not notably better compared to on-field. The methods used also ensured that at least 1 kg of composting substrate was in direct contact with the plastic samples in all cases. This point towards the potential role of other composting parameters such as the process scale, substrate composition and particle size distribution in the rate of disintegration. These factors may vary for different plants and seasonally. In addition, the presence and diversity of microorganisms play a role." (12a) In general, this research can be a great contribution to the literature and to the process of industrial composting of certain plastics. The research is clearly and accurately presented but some more fundamental and also recent papers should be cited to better explain the degradation of the plastics used in this study. Main factors that contribute to their degradation should be presented from the literature. (12b) In literature, PBS and even high molecular PLA degrades fast under thermophilic conditions in compost (Kale et al., 2007). However, in this study less than 5% of PLA blend was degraded in 3 weeks. Weren't samples in full contact with the compost due to mesh bags? Weren't they buried in the pile? The reasons of slower degradation rate in this study should be discussed more in detail and compared with literature. Is there any other study that contained samples in mesh bags, how long did it take for them to degrade? Thank you for the comment. To enhance the new version, fundamental papers on degradation mechanics as well as more comparable composting studies were described and cited in the Section "Introduction": paragraph 5 to 8. In addition, paragraphs 2, 3 and 4 of the Section "Differences in composting conditions between the lab-scale and on-field tests" were enhanced. The authors think that this risk is minimal as the samples in this study were fully

in contact with the organic waste as 1 kg of organic waste was enclosed together with the samples within the mesh bags. These bags were then placed in cages together with more organic waste. The cages were buried in the middle of the composting pile. A summary of other studies was added to Paragraph 5 and 6 on the introduction. In addition, a comparison with other studies of industrial composting was added to paragraph 6 of the Section "Disintegration rate in an industrial composting plant" though it should be noted that a direct comparison of on-field composting studies is difficult due to the differing sample dimensions, blend composition, substrate composition and general composting methods. References Cucina, M., Nisi, P. de, Trombino, L., Tambone, F., & Adani, F. (2021). Degradation of bioplastics in organic waste by mesophilic anaerobic digestion, composting and soil incubation. *Waste Management (New York, N.Y.)*, 134, 67–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2021.08.016> Kale, G., Auras, R., Singh, S. P., & Narayan, R. (2007). Biodegradability of polylactide bottles in real and simulated composting conditions. *Polymer Testing*, 26(8), 1049–1061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2007.07.006>

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